

Working together with construction industry for implementation of net-zero innovations – methodology and successful projects examples

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Summer school CARBON STORAGE IN NET ZERO CONSTRUCTION PRODUCTS Zlarin, Croatia 26-29 May 2025

SUMMER SCHOOL ← ▲ CARBON STORAGE IN NET ZERO CONSTRUCTION 26 - 29 MAY PRODUCTS ▲ 2025 ▲ → ISLAND ZLARIN

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TRL-scale

- *TRL 1 — Basic principles observed*
- *TRL 2 — Technology concept formulated*
- *TRL 3 — Experimental proof of concept*
- *TRL 4 — Technology validated in a lab*
- *TRL 5 — Technology validated in a relevant environment (industrially relevant in the case of key enabling technologies)*
- *TRL 6 — Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment (industrial environment in the case of key enabling technologies)*
- *TRL 7 — System prototype demonstration in an operational environment*
- *TRL 8 — System complete and qualified*
- *TRL 9 — Actual system proven in an operational environment (competitive market in the case of key enabling technologies, or in space)*

Figure 1 – Availability of resources for new product development at various TRLs. The gap in the middle referred to as “The Valley of Death” (REHVA Journal 52, 58-62)

Innovation project

Purpose

What is the purpose of the IP?

Development

Scope and sequence of the IP? Roles of leadership and division of labor. Align with collaborators and address dissenters.

Reflection

What worked? What could be done differently? What could be done better? What would you change?

Global, EU and Swedish market factors

SUMMARY MAP OF REGIONAL CARBON PRICING INITIATIVES

Source: World Bank. Data as of October 2022.

- ETS Implemented or scheduled for implementation
- ETS or carbon tax under consideration
- ETS Implemented or scheduled, ETS or carbon tax under...
- Carbon tax implemented or scheduled for implementation
- ETS and Carbon tax implemented or scheduled
- Carbon tax implemented or scheduled, ETS under consid...

Trilogue agreement on phase-out of free carbon allowances

With concurrent phase-in of CBAM

Source: European Parliament, Chart: Britta Weppner/Table Media

Swedish roadmap for cement industry

Zero-vision for Swedish cement production

Kg CO₂/ton cement

Standardization – if it is not in the standard....

Bilaga N (informativ)

Användning av andra bindemedel i en exponeringsklass än vad som anges i tabell 7 till 10 i en specifik betong

Anm. För användning av ett visst cement eller en viss bindemedelskombination för vilka krav på kvalifikationsprovning ställs i tabell 7 till tabell 9, se då bilaga T. Förfarandet i bilaga T är inte kopplat till en specifik betong.

RISE work in circularity of cement and concrete

BETCRETE 2019-2024 VINNOVA delfinansiering

- 2019 -2020 BETCRETE - (8 parter)
- 2020-2022 BETCRETE 2.0 (19-21 parter)
- 2022-2024 BETCRETE 3.0 (24-26 parter)

BETCRETE 2.0

BETCRETE 3.0

KPI:s

Goal

Produce a statistical basis for sustainability indicators and a system for reporting material flows in Sweden and by company

Result

Database and visualization

Short-term and long-term results and impacts:

Increases transparency and credibility among cement-concrete producers and contractors

Shows potential for improvement

Impact: relevant statistics that can be used for various analyses nationally and internationally

Relevant, representative and clear KPI:s 2020-2024

1. GWP (kg CO₂-eq/m³)
2. Proportion of alternative binders (%)
3. Binder amount (kg/m³)
4. Average strength class (MPa)
 - Ready-mixed concrete

Carbonated recycled aggregates

CO₂-sink of 20-50 % CO₂ of cement clinker¹

Methodology

- RCA - recycled concrete aggregate
- CDW - construction demolition waste

RCA with lower water absorption and higher strength

Flue gas ~12 % CO₂

Construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounts for **more than a third of all waste generated in the EU.**

In Sweden today, there is about **2 million tons of concrete waste** generated yearly.

Carbonation of washed ash

Based on the 110 000 tonnes of ash produced at RagnSells yearly, and the experimental data obtained in this study:

1) 14 895 tonnes of CO₂ captured

2) 53 102 tonnes of CaCO₃ produced

1. Price of PCC: ~294,44 EUR/ton (www.chemanalyst.com , 2023)

2. Price of CO₂: ~70,67 EUR/ton (<https://ember-climate.org/carbon-price-viewer/>)

3. Potential revenue: 16 688 064 EUR per year.

CO2Crete - Co-utilizing CO2 with mining, metallurgical, and construction wastes for concrete production: flipping environmental catastrophe to massive opportunities.

RI.
SE

BUILT ENVIRONMENT
MATERIAL DESIGN

+

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CO2Crete - Report WP2
CCUS sector analysis: assessment of carbonation potential in Sweden

Gry Møl Mortensen, Alex Oliva Rivera, & Placid Atongka Tchoffor
RISE Report 2025:9

Global CO₂ utilization market

- The global market for CO₂ utilization will reach USD 70 billion by 2030 and USD 550 billion by 2040
- Building materials will become the largest sector for CO₂ utilization, capturing 86% of the total market value by 2040.

Market size (billion dollars, USD)

Pathway	Market Size (Million Tonnes/yr)	Carbon Uptake Potential (Mt/yr)	TRL
Aggregates	53,200	3,600	9
Carbonated Concrete	16,500	1650	9
Methane	1100	3025	9
Ethanol	86.8	166	5
Methanol	80	110	9
CaCO ₃ (GCC)	75	33	7
Biodiesel	20	30	5
Di-methyl Ether	8	7.65	9
CaCO ₃ (PCC)	14	6.16	7
PPC	6	3	9
Polyols	10	2	9
Food-grade CO ₂	17	17	9

RISE supporting LeadIT for sustainable cement production in India

Cemvision ↗

ECOMETRIX

SaltX
Technology

affectus

AB TORKAPPARATER
THERMAL PROCESSING EQUIPMENT

Swedish
Energy Agency

RISE

Not one but all together!!!

Figur 3: Genomförande av betongbranschens färdplan

18th NCB International Conference & Exhibition on Cement, Concrete and Building Materials

Cementing the Net Zero Future

27-29 November, 2024
Yashobhoomi, IICC Dwarka
New Delhi, India

SOME HUMBLE AND KIND MESSAGES TO THE STUDENTS THINK ABOUT THE MERITS OF ACADEMIC VS INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH

7 QUESTIONS FOR STUDENTS

What matters most?	To understand things	To make them work
Why science for you?	For the progress of it	Developing inventions
Keeps you from sleeping?	A very complex equation	A customer's pain point
Your favorite paper?	Scientific publications	Patents
N° of topics in 10 years?	1-5	10-50
Options of job type?	Few opportunities	Many opportunities
Dream job in 15 years?	Professor	R&D Manager

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November, 2024
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Cementing the Net Zero Future

<p>KEY PARTNERS 🤝</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investors • Media Producers • Film Maker Guilds • Cinemas, Theaters • TV Networks • Amazon AWS • Consumer Electronic Companies • Regulators 	<p>KEY ACTIVITIES 🛠️</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology R&D • Content licensing • Content production • Content distribution • Data analytics • Sales and marketing 	<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS 💎</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 24/7 On Demand Entertainment • View high-definition shows and movies • Stream content • Unlimited access • Netflix Original • 30 Day free trial • No commercials 	<p>CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS ❤️</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self service • On-demand • Ease of use 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS 🎯</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Micro-segmentation • 2000 preference clusters • Usage • usage segmentation • Geographical • content/languages
<p>COST STRUCTURE 📉</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production • Research and Development • Licensing • Infrastructure - AWS • Marketing • Payment Processing Fees • General/Admin 	<p>REVENUE STREAMS 💰</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subscription Model • Product Placement • DVD Rental • Future Model - licensing Netflix owned content 			

KEY RESOURCES 🧰

- Brand
- Apps/website
- Platform
- Employees
- Film Makers/Producers
- Prizes/Awards

CHANNELS 🌐

- Any Device
- Netflix App
- Word of mouth
- Online advertising
- Offline advertising
- Social Media

AIRBNB BUSINESS MODEL

<p>KEY PARTNERS </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hosts • Hotels • Experience providers • Corporate travel partners • Travel managers • Investors/ Venture Capitalists • Lobbyists • Photographers • Maps • Cloud hosting - AWS 	<p>KEY ACTIVITIES </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Platform and technology development • Sales and marketing • Maintaining trust and brand reputation • Customer service/ experiences • Partner management 	<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS </p> <p>HOSTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income generation • Ease of listing • Calendar, booking system • Access to photographers <p>GUESTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low cost accommodation • Variety of choices/ locations • Variety of prices/budgets • Unique options <p>HOTELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to guests • Booking system <p>EXPERIENCE PROVIDERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income from guests • Platform/system 	<p>CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIPS </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-service • Own the relationship • Trust through verification • Tailored • Manage bad behaviour and risks 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS </p> <p>GUESTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • business travel guests • leisure travel guests <p>HOSTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Room unit/condo/house • House owners * Country/city/suburban/ city <p>EXPERIENCE PROVIDERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialists * Tour companies <p>PHOTOGRAPHERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Freelance photographers <p>HOTELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independent hotels • Hotel groups
<p>COST STRUCTURE </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost of acquisition • Weighted average cost of capital • R&D platform • Payment processing • Payroll/contractors • Infrastructure • Legal/insurance • Lobbying/PR • Customer support 		<p>REVENUE STREAMS </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service fee per transaction • Hosts commission charge • Hotel commission charge • Experience commission charge 		